

Dermatophytosis: An Overview

Sejal Antiya

Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Kamdhenu university, Anand- 388001

Introduction

Fungi causes various type of disease in human as well as in animals. There are large number of zoonotic fungi which affect the human. Dermatophytosis is disease of epidermal tissue of human or animals caused by the fungi called dermatophytes. They cause infection on skin, hair, horns, nails and feathers. Several species belong to the *Microsporum* and *Trichophyton* genera which is known as ringworm they are zoonotic in nature. There are three groups.

Zoophilic dermatophytes: Mostly found in animals but harmful to the human as well.

Geophilic dermatophytes: Mostly found in soil rarely infect the animal and human

Anthropophilic dermatophytes: Commonly found in human and affect the human

<i>Zoophilic dermatophytes</i>	Host
<i>Trychophyton equinum</i>	Horse, monkey, mule, man
<i>Trychophyton mentagrophytes</i>	Horse, goat, sheep, cattle, human, dog, rabbit, pig
<i>Trychophyton verrucosum</i>	Horse, goat, sheep, cattle, human, dog, rabbit, pig
<i>Trychophyton gallinae</i>	Birds, dog, cat, human
<i>Microsporum equinum</i>	Horse and human
<i>Microsporum canis</i>	Dog, human
<i>Microsporum distortum</i>	Cat, dog, monkey human
<i>Geophilic dermatophytes</i>	Host
<i>Microsporum nanum</i>	Pig, rarely man
<i>Microsporum gypseum</i>	Dog, horse, rarely man
<i>Anthropophilic dermatophytes</i>	Host
<i>Trychophyton rubrum</i>	Man and rarely animals
<i>Trychophyton audouinii</i>	Man and rarely animals

Epidemiology

Most commonly chances of getting infection are direct contact with infected host. In high

humidity weather fungal infection can be multiply. Young animals are more susceptible to the fungal infection compared to adult animals. People get infected by touching an animal who already carry fungal infection ringworm can be spread by animals like cattle, pig, dog, cats etc.

Clinical sign in animals

- Lesion developed on chest and limbs
- Lesion developed on dewlap and intra maxillary skin
- Hair loss, patches formation on skin
- Grey whitish crust formation
- Hyperpigmentation, erythema, papules, hair loss, nodular lesion observed

Clinical sign in human

- Symptoms developed after 4-15 days after touching infected host it includes:
- Itchy skin
- Rashes on skin
- Hair loss
- Scaly patches
- Development of lesion in single or multiple, round or oval primary on face, neck and arms
- Mycosis of feet, toe webs and hand

Diagnosis

- Diagnosis based on clinical sign and symptoms
- Direct microscopic examination of skin scraping
- Identification of fungus by fungal culture

Treatment

Fungal infection treatment may take time to recovery. Local treatment includes the removal of crusts by scrapping or brushing. Topical application of weak solution of iodine, whitfield's ointments, 10% ammoniated mercury ointment, ointment containing propionic, hexetidine etc. Systematic treatment includes the intravenous injection of sodium iodide and oral drug administration of griseofulvin may be useful in fungal infection.

Prevention and control

- Maintained personal hygiene
- Wash your hand after touching animals
- Isolation and treatment of infected animal
- Disinfection of premises
- Some kind of vaccine available in market for prevention of fungal infection
- Proper diet with essential vitamins supplement, vitamin A play major role in fungal infection
- Regular checkup of your pet or animal by veterinary doctor
- Keep your skin clean and dry
- Avoid personal items like towel, clothes with other

References

<https://www.cdc.gov/fungal/diseases/ringworm/symptoms.html>

<https://www.msdtvetmanual.com/integumentary-system/dermatophytosis/dermatophytosis-in-cattle>

